

DIGITAL TEACHING OF LISTENING SKILL IN SECOND LANGUAGE

Rajapova Ruzigul Mansurbek kizi¹,
Sultonova Mohigul Ziyoddin kizi²

Urgench state university Foreign language and
literature department

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ABSTRACT

It describes how teach listening comprehension in second language teaching in digital era. It also shows some digital materials to use in teaching listening skill and proves its beneficial points with the help of examples. It is highly recommended that foreign language teachers should utilize digital resources to get authentic materials.

INTRODUCTION

Language is such a communication tool that people can communicate with each other. Language can help to share ideas and knowledge among people. G. Broughton and et. all (1980) explained that humans are allowed to produce utterance, often quite novel, in great number of contexts by the means of language where they bend, mould, develop the language to fit ever-developing communicative needs. As it is comprehended that every aspect of life depends on the language. Nowadays there exist much more 7000 languages all over the world. It means that individuals communicate with each other in 7000 ways. Of course, it is difficult to learn all of them. But it is recommended to study one or several languages of famous ones.

No matter what kind of career a human has, she/he is in need of knowing a foreign language to develop his/her career way.

That's why, highly developed or highly developing countries are trying to create new convenient opportunities for both foreign language learning and teaching.

All in all, second language is regarded as a key of development of every sphere of life by sharing experiences and ideas other nations and countries.

Many scholars have created new ways of teaching foreign language with the help of various technologies. As a result, thanks to advanced technologies, the term of digital language teaching (DLT) has been coined in linguistics. DLT is the way of teaching foreign languages by the means of advanced technologies. The way of teaching has been used in linguistics since 20 th century. But the term of DLT has been used in linguistics sphere for half of a century.

DLT has opened a door of teaching second languages efficiently without any

difficulties in the modern world. Maggie Sokolik (2013) considered that digital technology can be a new battery of tools for instructors and students with which language can be learned effectively. It can be seen in the example of only internet. Because with the help of it, not only teachers but also students have had a chance to get large data base in natural foreign language atmosphere about teaching foreign language. Numerous websites about foreign language teaching have been created by native language teachers in collaboration with experienced technologists in the purpose of sharing language teaching experiences and innovative ways of teaching foreign language or providing information base to learn a second language in an easy way. A few years ago, R.G. Otero (2016) proved that an online tool should be created for teaching community members in order that they are able to share their ideas and resources which enrich this field while turning the experience of creating innovative resources into an easier task. Moreover, there exist online language courses organized by mother-tongue teachers that they motivate FLLs to learn any foreign language with the help of virtual natural language atmosphere.

Although many researches have not done on it yet, skillful teachers are managing to employ it to teach foreign language learners (FLLs). Because they have already been aware of its conveniences. According to Jack Richards (2015), TLLT (Technology for language learning and teaching) allows students to find learning materials that match their preferred way of learning, for example,

visual or auditory. It has helped significantly to teach their students online in every country during COVID 19. It was highly impossible to attend language classes in education rooms owing to quarantine rules. But there was a solution to the problem which could offer online classes for FLLs without any hesitations about health defences. Especially, the educational platform of Moodle was popular among universities at that moment. Eventhough the platform was created to for all of subjects, it made huge contribution to teach and assess FLLs online for foreign language teachers when it was impossible to organize traditional classrooms.

In general, digitalization of second language teaching has improved the quality of teaching and conveniences of it.

Although the language is a natural occasion, it is difficult to learn it. Because every language accent differs from another one. That's why, teaching listening skill seems more intricate for second language educators. Penny Ur (2012) explained that listening was taught in the purpose of enabling our students eventually to cope with natural listening situations that they are most likely to encounter in real life.

It is an actual fact that without good listening comprehension, SLLs can not gain speaking acquisition perfectly. In order to produce a speech, they have to receive imitations or proper pronunciations of sounds as well as words. So many scholars have conducted their researches on listening so as to help teachers to teach listening efficiently. So that they can instruct their students how to communicate with non-native speakers

and native speakers without any challenges.

As listening is the ability to comprehend sounds and oral speech in second language teaching, it requires more digitalization than other skills. Because to increase listening comprehension, teaching words in their standard citations forms is significantly essential to build up the learner's oral vocabulary but that by no means ensure that the learner will identify them successfully when they occur in connected speech (John Field, 2008). For this reason, we have to use DLT method to teach second language listening. Since listening deals with comprehending sounds, oral speech, it is the best way of teaching. Because some of English teachers can not pronounce the sounds or words correctly owing to the influence of their mother tongue accent. That's why, using a mixed variety of audio and video materials made by native speakers is useful to give SLLs proper instructions. David Nunan (2013) argued that any discussion of listening text probably needs to deal with the issue of authentic texts. With the help of digital technologies, we can get authentic resources.

There are some digital materials for teaching listening which can be found in authentic versions without any challenges.

- **Radio podcasts**

Nowadays it is not a problem to find radio podcasts by native speakers. They are the most convenient materials for improving second language listening comprehension. They also are available in all levels. Teachers should instruct their students to listen the radio podcasts and then ask what they comprehend from the material. By this way, the learners increase not only

listening comprehension but also short-term memory and concentration which are really necessary during listening.

- **TV shows**

There exist so many funny TV shows that are created in English. Watching them open the door of success in listening comprehension for the second language learners. Especially, if they manage to find English TV shows with subtitles, they can adapt to listen the English words in full sentences which can be pronounced insignificantly or in a reduced way.

- **Audiobooks**

Teachers may also utilise audiobooks to improve their students' ability in listening comprehension. Because these kinds of books never bore the learners, especially fiction ones. And also, they can be found in all levels.

- **Movies**

Movies are the best ways of entertainment for everyone. That's why, teachers should take this kind of interest of the learners into consideration and use to create ways of teaching listening in second language. Because it is not only entertainment tool but also second language study tool if teachers know how to use them.

- **Music**

As for music, it is much more efficient way of teaching listening comprehension for all levels. Because it can motivate the learners to study listening comprehension in foreign language with its colourful attractiveness. Particularly, listening rap music can increase the speed of brain comprehension while listening.

- **Online platforms**

There are so many online platforms intended for teaching listening. Lyrics

training can be an example of these kinds of platforms. The platform can help both to teach new vocabulary and to improve their learners' listening skills in immersive way. Lyrics training get music from You tube and asks learners to complete gaps in the blanks while they focus on lyrics. In addition to this, it is free of charge for everyone.

• **Apps intended for improving listening**

There are 2 apps of the most useful ones to help to enhance listening skills in English.

The highly-rated BBC Learning English app helps users improve their English listening, grammar, and speaking. We will be able to hear straightforward conversations from BBC Learning English

as well as 6-Minute English, English At Work, and also the English we have a tendency to Speak. Each lesson comes with English audio, a transcript, exercises, and a vocabulary list. Users may take a look at their English, chat with different English learners, and observe their English speaking with voice recognition.

Listening to podcasts could be a good way to be told English. Luke's English Podcast is very useful as a result of it's a feature that lets users speed up or curtail the playback. The podcasts even have transcripts on the market. In addition to swiftness down the playback, users will stop, pause, and repeat the podcasts. The app options new podcasts and also the full episode archives.

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